

Venkatasamy, R., J.O. Mbego and F.M. Opar (2006). Ensuring Sustainable Forest Management through Valorisation and Responsible Utilisation of Timber: Kenya–A Case Study

Abstract

The urgency to curtail deforestation in Africa has been of national and international concern in recent years. Population growth in most African countries has been rapid over the past 30 years, resulting in increased demands for land for food production, and wood for the manufacturing industries, shelter and energy. In Kenya, forests, which used to form about 3.4% of the total land cover, now stand at less than 2%. Excisions have been regular and replanting reduced. The consumption of wood per capita fell from 1.2 M³ to 0.9 M³ within a short period of 5 years, between 1995 and 2000, production falling by 46% in 1997 alone. This is the general trend in many African countries. Apart from demands for more land, the lack of a policy on wood utilisation has also contributed to excessive pressures on forests. Mis-utilisation, non-utilisation, under-utilisation and ineffective preservative treatment have resulted in unnecessary wastes. Wastage is high at all stages of processing, with no efforts to develop products that mainly utilise waste. The lack of a grading system results in high-grade timber being utilised for low-grade products. A sound policy aiming at intensifying forest management and optimising utilisation, reducing waste, encouraging waste utilisation and, especially, ensuring effective chemical treatment to greatly extend service lives of timbers, will certainly reduce pressures on forests and help in conserving existing resources.

Keywords: Kenya, Forests, Timber utilisation, Valorisation, Conservation, Sustainability, Development.

1.0 Introduction

The forest resources of Africa are still vast, in terms of both natural indigenous and plantation forests. Exploitation of durable indigenous hardwood species to supply a European market, which lacked such commodities, has undoubtedly been irrational and excessive in the past. Being valuable and in great demand, such timbers are still overexploited, since hardwood species from natural forests represent an immediate source of income in foreign exchange. The ban imposed on the exportation of round or unprocessed timber by a number of African countries was a sound decision, although it came rather late. However, it did not make a lot of difference since roughly squared, and in some cases, round timber, is still exported. Faced with the problem that indigenous species are slow-grown and difficult to establish, vast forests of exotic, fast-grown, non-durable softwood and hardwood species were created in many African countries, where the bulk of forest plantations presently consists of species of pine, cypress and eucalyptus.

In many African countries, including Kenya, wood has, in the past years, always been available in adequate quantities, populations small and wood-based industries few and of small capacities. That situation started changing some 30 years ago. These countries never realised what the impact of rapid growths in population, greater demands for agricultural land for food production and increasing use of timber, would be on existing forests. Consequently, there has been little planning to either increase the production potential of commercial forests, or ensure optimum utilisation of wood. In Kenya, timber processors and users, the authorities concerned, including the Forest Department, have all failed to understand the necessity for a

strong emphasis on the economic utilisation of forest products. Slow reactions have been one of the causes for the present shortages in timber. Education and training in technologies related to timber have been slow to develop, leaving timber processors and end-users lacking essential information on the economies and diseconomies of wood utilisation.

In a situation where little information is available about the properties of the material and no advice given to timber users, it is normal that wood is mis-utilised, under-utilised, or utilised inadequately protected, or not protected at all, in environments of high risks. What is important to note is that since the Forest Department has not come up with a policy on utilisation, wood-based industries, wood preservation plants, manufacturers of wood preservatives and surface coatings and end users, have seen no reason to participate in or contribute to the enhancement and promotion of the material. Training in Wood Science in the country, recently started, has been too much of an academic nature, and there are no institutions providing training of a practical nature better suited for wood-based industries. There is no Forest Products division within the Forest Department to ensure appropriate and economic utilisation of timber. Given the present situation that exists in the Forestry sector in Kenya, policies on forest management, to optimise production of high quality timber, and on effective and efficient timber utilisation would help in conserving forests that have so far been spared from excisions, and thereby sustain timber production through sound management practices.

2.0 The Forest Resources of Kenya

Kenya is a country where the population has grown from 10 million to over 28 million within the past three decades, and is still growing, uncontrolled. The demand for land for food production and human settlements has not only put tremendous pressures on forestlands, but also resulted in higher demands for timber for construction, veneer production, panel products, paper manufacture, posts, poles and, most important, energy. According to the Statistical Abstracts of the Central Bureau of Statistics of Kenya, about 80% of the country's energy is wood-dependant. Forestlands, which use to comprise about 3.4% of the total land area, have been reduced to less than 2%. Information from different sources mentions excisions of 6.9% between 1963 and 1980, and as much as 27.1% in 1992 alone. Although Government Statistics do not show any major reductions of forests between 1970 and 2002, on the ground the fact remains that excisions never stopped since 1963, and major forests will still be excised to give way to agriculture and settlements. In 1997, forests plantations decreased by 4% and production by 46%, and the trend must have continued into 2002. The per capita consumption of wood fell from 1.2 M³ in 1995 to 0.9 M³ in 2000, not because of reduced demands, but rather through shortages in supplies. There has not been any substantial replanting since the early 1980's; most forest nurseries are at present abandoned or inactive.

The demand for poles and posts, wood for energy and industrial roundwood has been steadily increasing over the years. The pulp and paper, and veneer and panel products industries have more than doubled their capacities over the past 10 years. The number of sawmills in the country has been increasing, the greater majority not achieving a recovery rate better than 15%. Effective wood preservation to extend service lives of timbers has been either lacking or inadequate. The overall result is that there is an actual scarcity of timber in the country at present, and severe shortages are likely in future. Hypothetical trends of past and future demands for timber in the country, as proposed by the Kenya Forestry Master Plan, are illustrated in Table 1. What the Kenya Forestry Master Plan (KFMP) does not explain is how the extra demands will be met, as forests are being reduced rather than increased. To sustain

future wood demands, the only alternatives that the Forest Department can resort to would have to rely on intensive tree breeding programmes to improve wood quality and yield, and maximal utilisation, including extension of life of timbers in service through effective and appropriate chemical treatment.

Table 1: Projected Wood Supply and Demand for Kenya - 1995-2020 (000M³)

YEAR	1995	2000	2005	2010	2015	2020
Total Wood Demand	22,384	26,592	30,760	35,251	39,924	44,880
Total Wood Supply	25,034	27,738	29,769	32,236	35,031	37,984
Surplus/Deficit	2,650	1,147	- 977	- 3,015	- 4,893	- 6,841

Source: Kenya Forestry Master Plan (1994)

3.0 Policies on Utilisation

Population growth with a resulting necessity to excise forestlands for food production and settlements is not a phenomenon that has affected not only Africa or Kenya alone, but also every single other country in the rest of the world. Given that more land is necessary for an ever-increasing population, there should at least be a National Policy to regulate timber production and utilisation in the country, or efforts towards proper and economic use of wood to ensure and guarantee future supplies. It is rather disconcerting that the Forestry Master Plan of Kenya (1994) is silent as to forest products utilisation. Any planning in forestry should also articulate on the best economical use of forest products, otherwise unplanned and uneconomic utilisation leading to unnecessary and excessive wastage will put too much pressures on forests in terms of supply and demand. Existing forests in the country may barely satisfy demands for the next few years, provided such demands are not irrational in that there is no gross mis-utilisation, non-utilisation or under-utilisation and service lives of timbers are substantially increased by effective preservation.

Although there are no immediate recipes to immediately accelerate progress in the field of economic and sound utilisation of timber in Kenya, there should at least be efforts to initiate such a process. In the first instance, efforts should emanate from the producers of the commodity, the Forest Department, then filtered on to the users. Unfortunately, after having sold the tree, the Forest Department shows no interest as to what happens to the wood. This results in a situation where the producer hardly knows whom he is producing for and whether his products are being utilised in such a way as to justify producing more of the same quality and in the same quantity.

3.1 Quality and Quantity

Quality and quantity pose other problems, which the producer (the Forest Department) cannot resolve easily. The user cannot complain to the producer about the quality of the product. The producer is not concerned about the quality of the product, but more interested in volumes produced as fast as possible, to satisfy demands. Neither is the producer under obligation to ensure that the product adheres to some specifications with regards to quality or grade, as there have not been any such requirements from processors or end-users. The product is

defined only in terms of species, size and quantity. Processors and end-users do not appear to be aware that they can specify on the quality of the product they require, or would like to purchase.

As populations increase, so will development and the demand for timber. If to supply the increasing demands the producer was to solely resort to planting more and felling more trees, then such an approach will not work, as there will not be any surplus land to plant more trees. Increasing forest plantations appears to be what the KFMP (1994) recommends. Increases in populations normally result in higher demands for food, hence higher pressures on land, and excising more and more from forestlands. The producer must then resort to other strategies in management to increase production within the existing constraints and ensure that his products are of a quality that will result in optimal use and minimal wastage. The producer must also ensure that his products are durable or long lasting, be it through natural or artificial methods, so that the user does not keep coming back for replacements. That is as much as asking for a drastic change in the existing concepts of forest management and silvicultural practices in the country. Kenya would not be the first country to have to resort to such changes, as that has been done in Europe and North America, to meet increasing demands from growing populations.

3.2 Mis-Utilisation, Under-Utilisation and Non-Utilisation

An important problem, which has not been addressed yet, is proper and economic utilisation of forest products, because of the lack of policies on utilisation of wood in the country. A good policy on utilisation should start by grading and classifying timber for specific end uses, be it posts, poles, pulpwood, sawn wood, veneer logs, or wood for energy. A second necessity is to reduce waste to the minimum, with the possibilities of waste utilisation. Finally, timbers, especially non-durable timbers used outdoors or in ground contact, should be made to last longer through appropriate chemical treatments.

3.2.1 Mis-Utilisation

The tradition of felling large diameter eucalyptus trees for splitting to be used as fencing posts has not yet been seen as wasting timber which should be better utilised for producing structural members and sawnwood. Unless of course if such trees are over-mature with many defects and the timber of a quality or grade unsuitable for any other uses. Mature eucalyptus is a preferred material for structural members and low-cost furniture. The timber is better utilised and fetches a better price when used for the latter purposes. In the same way, large diameter logs, which should go to sawmillers or for veneer peeling, are chipped for pulp and paper production. Timber of the quality for pulpwood, or chipboard and fibreboard manufacture, is most of the time used as fuelwood or rejected as non-utilisable waste. It is common to see good grade sawn timber used in the manufacture of blockboard or batten board, when shorts are available in large quantities. These are a few of the typical examples of mis-utilisation of wood by wood-based industries in the country and timber users in general.

Mis-utilisation is a problem, which can be only resolved if there is a National Policy about utilisation of forest products. Elsewhere Standards clearly define the class and grades of timber that should go to different end users. Pulpwood falls under the category of “*small diameter timber, thinnings, tree tops and branches*”. The raw material for chipboard, fibreboard and flakeboard consists of “*thinnings, tree tops, slabs, shorts and large industrial residues*”. In addition, what regulates the market apart from Policies and Standards is the pricing of the raw material. Large diameter logs (sawn and veneer materials) are more costly

to produce than small diameter timber. The price of the raw material is also reflected on the price of the end product. There is no differentiation in pricing in Kenya as timber is sold in terms of volumes, not diameter classes and grades. Such a policy obviously encourages mis-utilisation. Why should the paper or the chipboard industries bother about small diameter timber, shorts, slabs, or industrial waste, when they are obtaining large diameter logs cheaply? If there was pricing according to grades, then certainly manufacturers of cheaper products would utilise the cheaper raw materials. There may be arguments that it is up to the buyer to utilise the material as he wishes. Wood is an industrial raw material, the bulk of which is produced by the State. The material should be properly utilised to produce goods necessary for the development and well being of the nation or for export. It must therefore be utilised for optimum yields in terms of monetary returns and quality of life.

3.2.2 Under-Utilization

Under-utilisation results in the loss and wastage of a substantial amount of wood in almost every African country. One example in Kenya where such losses are quite high is found in the softwood plantations. Proper silvicultural practices dictate that thinning and pruning should be carried out at laid down intervals to allow the best trees to grow into a final mature crop of high quality timber that will fetch a high price. At the same time, small diameter trees are removed at intervals and sold for appropriate end uses, a necessary return on investments. In Kenyan plantations, small diameter cypress or pine removed as thinnings are rarely utilised. In fact, there is no industry that specifically relies on thinnings. In most plantations thinning is rarely carried out, small diameter trees become suppressed, die out and rot in the forest. In the same way tree tops and large branches are left on site after clearfelling. These are prescribed raw materials for pulp and paper and chipboard manufacture in many other countries, but considered as un-utilisable waste in this country.

Wastage starts from the time a tree is felled. Marcotte (1993) worked out that, in France, about 50% to 55% of a tree is wasted in the form of branches, chips from felling cuts and stumps, with an average processing recovery rate of 48.5%. In Kenya, apart from losses incurred in the forest, more losses occur during conversion and processing. The average recovery rate in most Kenyan sawmills is below 20%, a few larger sawmills rarely achieving 40%. The reason for such low recovery is mainly due to the equipment and techniques used. Thick, large diameter circular saws are popular with many sawmillers, producing wide kerfs and resulting in large amounts of waste in the form of sawdust. Further, sawing is often inaccurate in terms of both straightness and size. More waste is consequently generated through planing or thicknessing to finished sizes. Slabs, sawdust, offcuts, shorts and planer shavings have little or no economical uses in Kenya. Sawdust and shavings are usually disposed of by burning, as these are regarded as a nuisance rather than industrial raw material; slabs and a substantial amount of shorts are used in low cost structures and for fencing. Being non-durable and used untreated, they rot in very short periods of time in service.

High waste production and low waste utilisation are two problems, which have to be carefully studied and corrected. There must be a policy concerning the licensing of sawmills with regards to equipment used and recovery rates. Under any normal circumstances, any Industry that unnecessarily wastes a country's resources and raw materials should not be allowed to operate. Waste production is not restricted to African countries alone. It is produced in industrialised countries of the West, but in smaller amounts, most of which is utilised. Types of waste and percentages of the same used for manufacturing other products in France, according to Marcotte (1993), are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Uses of Waste Generated by Wood-Based Industries in France (Million Tons)

Type of waste	Pulp and Paper	Panel Products	Energy	Charcoal	Horticulture Agronomy	TOTAL	% Recycled
Bark	--	--	230	--	420	650	62.3
Sawdust	--	586	150	--	170	906	59.3
Slabs	667	440	--	230	--	1337	98.6
Offcuts	30	90	40	70	--	230	30.7
Shavings	1706	435	16	--	--	2157	41.1
TOTAL	2403	1551	436	300	590	5280	74.5
% USED	45.5	29.4	8.3	5.7	11.2	--	--

Source: Marcotte (1998)

3.2.3 Non-Utilization

The diseconomies of non-utilisation becomes too obvious with the realisation that, on average, about 60% of planted trees (small diameter thinnings) are not utilised, 60% of mature trees are left in the forest as tops, branches, chips and stumps and finally 80% of the log is wasted during conversion. It is not easy to put a monetary value on losses resulting from non-utilisation but the amount must be substantial in African countries. There is a huge market for fencing posts in Kenya. Pine and cypress posts are shunned because these timbers are non-durable. But given the proper preservative treatment, they will last as long and even longer in the ground than the poorly treated, moderately durable species commonly used. All that is required is proper treatment schedules, adequate penetration and retention, and confidence in the product, the method of treatment and the chemical used.

Non-utilisation of small diameter trees has been justified because of higher exploitation and transportation costs. Some countries import small diameter timber for pulping. On-site chippers are available, enabling transportation of only clean chips to the mill. Small diameter trees, treetops, large branches and large Industrial residues produce high quality boards as long as the techniques of production are efficient, and all these are cheaper raw materials

Waste utilisation has not yet been considered in Kenya, as well as in many other African countries. Non-utilisation is mainly a matter of convenience as it is far too easy to collect large diameter logs from one site than to have a number of collection points. The utilisation of sawdust has been hardly looked into. However, sawdust is a raw material of great potential and has many uses, none of them exploited in Kenya, where it is produced in large amounts and regarded as a nuisance.

It is difficult to assign responsibilities as to proper utilisation of forest products in Kenya without going back to the producer, that it is the Forest Department. The role of the Forest Department is not only to guarantee a continuous supply of timber to satisfy the requirements of consumers, but also to ensure that once the standing trees are sold, the wood is utilised to the maximum with minimal waste. The Forest Department, together with wood-based industries and timber users should work out a clear and practical policy on utilisation. To formulate a policy would not be too difficult, but to implement the same would require the

formation of another branch of the Forest Department, a Forest Products Division, with a Utilisation and Marketing Office and Utilisation Officers. The Forest Department has a network of foresters at different levels and grades to properly manage State forests. Foresters are not trained to manage forest products. There are however trained Wood Scientists in the country who can be entrusted with the responsibility of ensuring that timber is graded for the appropriate end uses, utilisation optimal, and wastage at any and every stage of production and processing reduced to the minimum.

4.0 Improving Service Lives of Timbers

Commercial Forestry, all over the world, has resorted to fast growing, non-durable species, as demands for timber keep increasing and durable species take too long to attain maturity. Increasing demands for timber can only be met by short rotation forest crops, mainly softwoods. Non-durable species have several disadvantages over durable species, all too well known. However, non-durable species can be chemically treated to give long and adequate service lives. Service lives of over 30 years for properly treated timbers used in ground contact are common in many countries. Even if there were to be available sources of durable species in any country, a policy on classification as to most appropriate and economic use of such timbers must be in place.

The trend around the world is that adequately treated non-durable timbers are channelled to such end uses as posts and poles in ground contact (high risks environments) and as interior or exterior out-of-ground construction timbers (low risks environments). Untreated, they find their way to the pulp and paper industry, for veneer peeling, blockboard, chipboard, fibreboard and other panel products manufacture. Timber can thus be utilised intelligently and economically.

None of the industries relying on wood as a raw material in Kenya has ever shown any interest in investing in research and development. The wood preservation industry, which can and should have contributed to conserving forests and sustaining timber supplies through effective preservation, has never been interested in investigating new techniques, new products, testing treated material or in education and training or in advising timber users. The few wood preserving chemicals used in the country are imported in bulk by wood treaters, a limited but expensive range being available in the do-it-yourself outlets. Other locally concocted mixtures with little or no protective effects on wood are widely sold and used, reflecting on the lack of information about wood preserving chemicals in the country. There is also little and inadequate information about the benefits of effective wood preservation. Treated products are not tested, there being no testing laboratories or long-term testing sites. The wood preservation industry should have been at the forefront of such testing, but that has never been the case. Creosote and CCA pressure-treated eucalyptus transmission and telegraph poles have service lives of 5 to 15 years in Kenya, according to a report by Venkatasamy (2000). In Tanzania failure of treated poles after 6 months to 2 years in service is common (Murira, 1988). Given the number of poles that have to be constantly replaced as a consequence of ineffective preservation, it is easy to visualise, apart from monetary losses, the unnecessary and irresponsible drain on eucalyptus plantations in these two countries alone.

5.0 Discussion and Conclusion

Two realities, which have been allowed to persist in the country, need mentioning:

1. The population of the country has been growing at too high a rate to be comfortably sustained by the country's resources. Control over population growth has not been attempted.
2. There has been no change in Forest Management practices towards effective tree management, linked with wood quality and end-product uses, with the objective of sustaining quality wood supplies.

That is as much as saying that the problem could have been averted. However, the immediate objective should aim at correcting the imbalance without disturbing the human and natural environments. Perhaps a good start would be at drafting and implementing a sound policy on wood utilisation. Economic utilisation of wood has as objective cost-effective and value-added timber management. The present situation where the Forest Department manages the trees but not the timber cannot be allowed to persist. Forest resources around the world keep changing in terms of quantity and quality. The policy is to use existing resources more efficiently and get more value out of it. Without a Forest Products division with an executive mandate to evaluate wood quality for optimal processing and end uses, forestry practices would fail in one important mission: sustain quality wood supplies in the framework of sustainable forestry.

Wastage, whether through mis-utilisation, non-utilisation, under-utilisation or ineffective preservation, is a serious problem that needs immediate curtailment. Waste utilisation has not been an area for serious consideration yet. What is normally considered as waste in the wood processing industries has a recoverable and utilisation value. Bark, sawdust, slabs, offcuts, shavings and other large industrial residues are all raw materials for quality and marketable products in many countries. Non-utilisation of waste in Kenya is probably the result of a lack of ideas from entrepreneurs and industrialists.

Wood preservation has reached a stage in development in other countries where effectively treated timbers in ground contact will be expected to have service lives of up to 60 years. It is inadmissible that in Kenya treated utility poles barely last for 5-15 years; chemicals and techniques used being the same that achieve much longer service lives in other countries. Why the situation is what it is and why it has been allowed to persist for the past 40-50 years is difficult to comprehend. Neither is it easy to understand how industrial oils can be branded as wood preservatives and openly marketed as such, with no interference from the Kenya Bureau of Standards or other regulating bodies in the country. Simpler techniques of treatment and cheaper chemicals have not been introduced to rural areas of the country, where the greater amount of timber is used. It is difficult to identify the relevant institution which should have been responsible to oversee and regulate wood preservation in the country.

Wood utilisation and wood preservation have been left solely in the hands of entrepreneurs with little or no government control or interference. Such businesses are purely profit-oriented, rarely concerned about sustainable management of forests or conservation. It is also well known that wood-based industries in the country have been insular and secretive. They have no organisations to be used as platforms for exchange of ideas or technology transfer and they do not interact with the Universities, Research Institutions or researchers, whether local or foreign. Most of the industries are hardly in touch with development outside the country, a situation that does not contribute to development and progress. There must be participation in

development rather than simple consumption of the country's resources. Drafting policies on sound and economic utilisation may be a simple task, but it must also involve all timber users. To sustain forests and conserve resources there must be a commitment from all those depending on timber, through goodwill and a sense of responsibility, supported by Codes of Practice and enforceable Regulations. That is the challenge facing the Forestry sectors, timber producers from the private sectors, wood processors, treaters and end-users all over Africa today.

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